

number of cane plants caused by favorable temperature in April as well as by the residual effect of potato on cane plants. The commercial cane sugar (CCS) percentage in cane was more or less identical under different cropping

systems. Overall performance for yield and economic returns of rice, potato, and sugarcane were higher under the inter/relay cropping system of sugarcane + rice-potato (preferably with

transplanted plantlets) than under the sole cane crop. This method can be successfully adopted by small and marginal farmers after the May harvest of late-sown wheat. ■

Farm machinery

Rice-cum-green manure culture with modified drum seeder under lowland condition

P. Rajendran, A. Tajuddin, and C. Ramaswami, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We initially investigated *Sesbania aculeata* as an intercrop in wet-seeded rice. Compared with rice alone, rice intercropped with green manure (GM) had a yield advantage when GM was incorporated at about 35-40 cm height. Mean height of the rice crop was 32 cm. Further work is required, however, to find cheaper ways of incorporating GM and weeding to reduce cultivation costs.

A modified seeder was developed based on the IRRI drum seeder design (Fig. 1). The seeder was field-tested in a 0.03-ha unreplicated plot in 1998. It has two wheels and sows rice and GM in alternate rows 12.5 cm apart. The seeder width is 0.75 m. The walking speed is around 1.5 km h⁻¹. Including time loss for unhooking and hooking the handle after each pass, two men can cover 0.54 ha d⁻¹. The advantages of the seeder are shown in Table 1.

The low seeding rate of GM (20 kg ha⁻¹) was due to seed availability.

The GM intercrop was trampled both manually and by using the IRRI single-row conoweeder at 36 DAS (Fig. 2). Table 2 shows the benefits of the technology.

This trial indicated the possibility of intercropping rice with GM as a potentially useful technology. Fine-tuning of the intercropping technology considering rice duration, cultivation season, and location is the focus of future research. ■

Table 1. Advantages of the seeder.

	Modified seeder for rice + GM intercropping	Transplanting rice
Duration, wet biomass addition, seeding rate of GM	36 d, 7 t ha ⁻¹ , and 20 kg ha ⁻¹ , respectively	Advantage of dual cropping does not exist
Green manure height and number of nodules plant ⁻¹	40 cm and 35, respectively	-
Rice establishment charges over same preparatory cultivation	\$15 ha ⁻¹ ^a	\$100 ha ⁻¹

^aIncludes additional cost for proper leveling.

Table 2. Benefits of using the modified seeder.

	Trampling-cum-weeding by IRRI single-row conoweeder	Manual trampling
Labor requirement (man-days)	18 ha ⁻¹	54 ha ⁻¹
Cost involved ha ⁻¹	US\$14	US\$42
Additional benefit compared with no intercrop	Weeds are buried completely, thereby adding more organic matter.	

1. A modified IRRI drum seeder. (Net weight = 17 kg, wheel diameter = 60 cm, drum diameter = 20 cm).